

Statistical analysis of data from a sustainable community development project in Vietnam

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The ethnic minorities in the mountain areas of Vietnam have poor educational conditions, low income and small profit. These areas are among the poorest nationwide. ADDA aim to help these people with knowledge on sustainable agricultural practices and to make them realize that it is productive to meet and discuss problems and together find solutions that will affect the local society.

ADDA has been implementing a sustainable community development project, financed by Danida, in six different provinces of Vietnam since 2007 with the aim of achieving increased local agricultural production. The project has trained 15.400 maize farmers through the participatory Farmer Field Schools (FFS) where they were taught improved cultivation techniques along with the benefit of collaboration.

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Picture 1: Locals in their traditional clothing.

Picture 2: During FFS the farmers had some training fields where they tested the new techniques.

Among other to plant the maize seed with greater distance and thereby use less seed overall. The community development facilitators that train the locals are selected among the minority groups and therefore they speak the local language. Furthermore they have been through a training program to obtain the needed skills.

The data used in the current project is collected among 300 randomly selected farmers, 50 from each province. The farmers were among other questions asked of the yield of their fields before and after they have participated in FFS.

To make the best analysis possible it is important to decide exactly which variables that should be used. As the suggested success can be measured on extra maize harvested after the participation in FFS, the variable Yield will act as the response variable. Interesting variables to test whether they describe the variation in Yield will be the amount of seed used, province,

The important variables describing the variation in Yield is first and foremost FFS with the highest effect, which tells that there is a very significant difference from before and after the farmers participated in the training programs. The new techniques and knowledge the farmers have achieved have had a big impact on their yield from the maize fields.

Province is likewise an important explanatory variable and do interact with FFS, that is, the FFS effect is statistically different from province to province. The dependence of $\log(\text{Maize area})$ is also different from province to province.

FFS (before after training) and size of maize area. Furthermore the variable Farmer no. (farmer id) will be used as a random effect in the model. To obtain a normal distribution of Yield and Maize area a log transformation is made for both variables.

From the above figure it can be concluded that provinces with a high yield before FFS have improved little. The province difference in Yield from before and after FFS differentiated by maize area. The province difference were more distinct before participation in FFS since more red while provinces that performed poorly have shown major improvements. Therefore more provinces are similar in amount of Yield after FFS.

Interaction plot of Seed and Yield, respectively. The variables are differentiated by Province and before and after the participation of FFS.

The Son La province has even though they had a high yield before managed to improve even more and is by far the province that produce most maize since they have the biggest fields as well. Nghe An has made big improvements after FFS and is now the province that produce second-most maize. Ha Tinh is the province that had a very low yield before and even though they have almost doubled up their production they still perform poorly.

It is concluded that the sustainable community project has been a success and it could be interesting to implement the project other places around the world.